

The Power of Emotive Speech: Affecting of Words People's Feelings

*Mukhammadieva Nigina Makhmudovna*¹

Abstract: Emotiveness is the quality that makes a writer or speaker's feelings clear. By no means should expressiveness be equated with emotiveness; expressiveness is a more expansive concept. Emotive is used with regard to something that makes you have intense feelings rather than just having intense feelings. For example, an emotive conversation will result in getting people's emotions riled up, while an emotional conversation is one in which people go into it with a lot of intense feelings already.

Key words: emotiveness, speech, expression, negative and evil words, emotive speech.

When we talk to each other, the words we choose can make a big difference in how our message is understood. Emotive speech is when we use language that expresses feelings and emotions. In this text, we will explore the specific features of emotiveness in speech and some expressions that are connected to them. Understanding emotive speech is important because it helps us communicate better with others, making our conversations more engaging and meaningful.

Each of us has been in a situation where you carefully choose the words to hit your abuser more painfully. When they hurt you the same way. When you said the words, and they made your interlocutor smile and rejoice, you saw the interest in their eyes. And how warm it felt to hear someone's kind words addressed to you.

We know and say a lot of words that make you feel good, you want to smile, and pleasant associations arise. And there are those that cause sadness, aggression, despair. Both of them can stay in our memory for a long time, constantly surfacing, causing the corresponding emotions. Negative and evil words are like lightning bolts that wound, maim, and sometimes lead to death. For example: "I hate", "I would kill", "I want to destroy". These words emit a strong vibration that seems to knock the ground out from under your feet. The words spoken in the hearts carry the most powerful charge.

Positive, approving expressions can support a person, give strength and give confidence, good mood and joy, make them truly happy. For example: "You are an interesting conversationalist!", "When you are around, I feel calm and good!", "I am glad that there are people like you!".

It turns out that what we think about is what we talk about. At the same time, we put certain vibrations into each word. They include a whole range of feelings and emotions: delight, humor, benevolence or anger, hatred, envy. It is from these components that the power of the word is formed. Therefore, you should not rush with servants, but use them with caution.

The word is the expression of our thoughts. There is a huge amount of information in every word. All the words are emotionally colored. According to the vocabulary of a person, his speech, it is possible to determine the level of his development, education, well-read, his social and professional status, prospects for further development, the ability to achieve results, attitude to people and communication with them. The project is dedicated to the study of the influence of words on people's daily lives. Words play a huge role, reflecting thoughts and emotions, influencing others and shaping our behavior. Studying this topic will allow you to understand more deeply how words affect our lives and the lives of others.

¹ Teacher of History and philology department of Asia International university

Idea

Explore how words shape thoughts and emotions, influence people's behavior and create a certain way of life.

Goal

To investigate and analyze the influence of words on everyday life, to identify the mechanisms of their impact on human behavior.

Problem

Many people do not realize the full power of the influence of words on their behavior and life in general. Studying this topic will allow you to choose words more consciously and control their impact on yourself and others.

Target audience

People interested in the influence of language on behavior and life, experts in the field of psychology and linguistics.

Tasks

1. To conduct a literary review on the topic of the influence of words on everyday life.
2. Conduct a survey among people of different ages and socio-cultural status about the impact of words on their lives.
3. Analyze the data obtained and identify the main mechanisms of the impact of words on human behavior.

Roles in the project

Researcher, analyst, sociologist

Resources

Information resources for literary review, access to educational institutions or sociological centers for conducting a survey, computer equipment for data analysis.

Product

A study of the influence of words on everyday life in the form of a scientific article that will contain a literary review, survey results and analysis of the data obtained.

Emotive speech is any language that conveys emotions. This can include happiness, sadness, anger, excitement, or fear. When we speak with emotion, we create a connection with our listeners. For example, when a friend tells us about their day, using words that show how they felt can make the story more interesting. Instead of saying, "I was happy," they might say, "I was overjoyed!" The word "overjoyed" expresses a stronger feeling and helps us understand their emotions better. There are 4 features of emotive speech

1. *Choice of Words:* The words we pick can greatly influence the feelings we express. For instance, saying "I am sad" is different from saying "I am heartbroken." The second phrase uses a more powerful word that shows deeper emotion.
2. *Tone of Voice:* How we say something can be just as important as what we say. A cheerful tone can make a simple statement sound exciting. For example, if someone says, "I won a prize!" in an excited voice, it makes us feel happy for them.
3. *Body Language:* Our body language also helps convey our emotions. For instance, if someone is talking about something scary while shaking their hands and looking worried, it shows that they feel frightened. Combining words, tone, and body language helps to create a full picture of what someone is feeling.

1. Expressions and Idioms: Certain expressions and idioms can add emotiveness to our speech. Phrases like "walking on air" or "feeling blue" are examples of how we can describe feelings in a more vivid way. These expressions not only convey the emotion but also create a mental image that helps listeners understand better.

Using emotive speech can make our communication more effective. Here are some reasons why it is important:

- *Building Connections*: When we express our feelings, it helps others relate to us. If we share our happiness, it can spread joy to those around us. Similarly, sharing sadness can create empathy and understanding.
- *Persuasion*: In arguments or persuasive speeches, emotive language can be powerful. For example, if someone is trying to convince others to help the environment, they might say, "If we don't act now, we are leaving a terrible world for future generations!" This use of emotion can encourage listeners to take action.
- *Enhancing Creativity*: Emotive speech can make stories and poems more captivating. Authors often use emotive language to evoke feelings in their readers. For example, a poem about a lost pet might use words like "lonely" and "heartbroken" to express deep sorrow.

Here are some common expressions connected to emotions:

- *Happy*: "On cloud nine," "full of joy," "bouncing off the walls."
- *Sad*: "Down in the dumps," "heavy-hearted," "feeling blue."
- *Angry*: "Seeing red," "boiling over," "fuming."
- *Excited*: "Jumping for joy," "on the edge of my seat," "pumped up."

Using these expressions can help us communicate our emotions more clearly.

Emotive language is not reserved for literature either. It is used in everyday interactions as well.

Oftentimes, news headlines use emotive language to hook the audience.

Here are a few examples.

- An innocent bystander was murdered in cold blood in Downtown Chicago.
- The words "innocent" and "murdered" and the phrase "in cold blood" are the uses of emotive language in this sentence.
- A monster of a man violated an underage girl.
- The words "monster," "violated," and "underage" are the uses of emotive language in this sentence.
- The defenseless victims were attacked in the cover of night.
- The phrases "defenseless victims" and "cover of night" and the word "attacked" are the uses of emotive language in this sentence.

In each example the emotive words do not need to be used to communicate a fact. However, this diction creates an emotional response in the audience.

In conclusion, emotive speech is a powerful tool in communication. By choosing the right words, using an appropriate tone, and combining body language with expressions, we can better express our emotions and connect with others. Understanding the features of emotiveness in speech can help us become better communicators, whether we are sharing stories, persuading others, or expressing our feelings. So next time you talk, think about how your words can impact those around you, and remember the power of emotive speech!

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